

Chloromethylation of Some Phenolic Compounds

K. P. Mathai and Suresh Sethna

Resacetophenone, methyl β -resorcylate, 4-nitroresorcinol, 2-nitroresorcinol, 4,4'- and 2,2'-dihydroxy-biphenyls and their methyl ethers have been chloromethylated with different molecular proportions of paraformaldehyde in either acetic acid or dioxan medium. Structures of the chloromethyl derivatives have been established by reduction to the known methyl derivatives or oxidation to the known carboxylic acids.

The present work deals with the chloromethylation of some substituted resorcinol derivatives and biphenols and their methyl ethers.

Resacetophenone on chloromethylation with one or more moles of paraformaldehyde gave a mixture of products from which no pure compound could be isolated. Its dimethyl ether with 1.2 moles of paraformaldehyde in dioxan at room temperature, however, afforded the 5-chloromethyl derivative which on oxidation with alkaline permanganate furnished 4,6-dimethoxyisophthalic acid¹, as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained on oxidation of methyl 2,4-dimethoxy-5-acetylbenzoate² with alkaline permanganate. On chloromethylation with excess of paraformaldehyde in glacial acetic acid at room temperature, the 3,5-dichloromethyl derivative was obtained.

Methyl β -resorcylate on chloromethylation with one mole of paraformaldehyde did not afford a pure product but with an excess of paraformaldehyde in dioxan at room temperature it furnished the 3,5-dichloromethyl derivative. The dimethyl ether of methyl β -resorcylate with 1.2 moles as well as with an excess of paraformaldehyde at 80-90° provided the 5-chloromethyl derivative which on oxidation gave rise to 4,6-dimethoxyisophthalic acid.

Chloromethylation of 4-nitroresorcinol did not provide a pure product, but its dimethyl ether furnished with one mole and with an excess of paraformaldehyde the 5-chloromethyl derivative which on oxidation afforded 2,4-dimethoxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid, identical with an authentic specimen prepared by methylation of the known 2,4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid³. The chloromethyl derivative on reduction with tin and HCl yielded 2,4-dimethoxy-5-methylamine, identical with the product obtained on nitration of 2,4-dimethoxytoluene and subsequent reduction with tin and HCl. Along with the chloromethyl derivative, a chlorine-free product was also isolated. Its analysis indicated that it might be bis-(2,4-dimethoxynitrobenzene)methylene. It has not been investigated further.

2-Nitroresorcinol on chloromethylation with one mole of paraformaldehyde gave a monochloromethyl derivative which could only be the 3-chloromethyl-2,6-dihydroxy-

1. Eijkman *et al.*, *Chem. Weekblad*, 1905, 2, 59, 70.

2. Trivedi and Sethna, *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 245.

3. Parikh and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1943, IIA, Part 5, p. 101.

nitrobenzene. With an excess of paraformaldehyde at room temperature it afforded the 3,5-dichloromethyl derivative. The dimethyl ether of 2-nitroresorcinol on chloromethylation at 70-80° furnished 2,6-dimethoxy-3-chloromethylnitrobenzene.

4,4'-Dihydroxybiphenyl on chloromethylation, using 2.5 moles of paraformaldehyde in dioxan at room temperature, provided a dichloromethyl derivative to which the 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-dichloromethylbiphenyl structure was tentatively assigned.

4,4'-Dimethoxybiphenyl on chloromethylation with two or more moles of paraformaldehyde in 90% acetic acid on a steam bath afforded the 3,3'-dichloromethyl derivative. On oxidation in acetic acid with potassium permanganate, it afforded an acid, identical with the one obtained on oxidation of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl⁴ with alkaline permanganate.

2,2'-Dihydroxybiphenyl did not provide a pure product on chloromethylation. Its dimethyl ether, however, gave the 5,5'-dichloromethyl derivative at room temperature. On oxidation it afforded an acid, identical with 2,2'-dimethoxybiphenyl-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid⁵ which was obtained in the present work by the Ullmann reaction on methyl 3-iodo-4-methoxybenzoate⁶ and subsequent hydrolysis of the ester.

The chloromethyl derivatives were subjected to the Sommelet reaction with hexamethylenetetramine. The methyl ethers provided formyl derivatives, whereas the hydroxy compounds gave unworkable products.

Most of the chloromethyl derivatives have been converted into their acetoxyethyl derivatives and some have also been converted into cyanomethyl and methoxyethyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for Chloromethylation.—HCl gas was passed through a mixture of paraformaldehyde and dioxan or acetic acid at room temperature till saturation. The substance was added and more HCl passed for 30 minutes. The chloromethyl product separated on keeping overnight. Where it did not separate, the reaction mixture was diluted with water when acetic acid was the solvent, or with light petroleum when dioxan was the solvent, or the dioxan was evaporated at room temperature and the chloromethyl product collected. Most of the chloromethyl derivatives were found to be highly soluble in common organic solvents, but sparingly soluble in light petroleum and insoluble in water (Table I).

General Procedure for the Sommelet Reaction.—The chloromethyl derivative in chloroform was heated over a water bath for 2 hrs. with hexamethylenetetramine. The separated complex was heated with dilute acetic acid over a steam bath for 6 hrs. and kept overnight. The separated formyl derivative was crystallised from either benzene or ethanol (Table III).

4. Boon-Long, *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, **43**, 5018.

5. Gilman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1963.

6. Nicolau, *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 16858.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE I

Chloromethyl derivatives.

S. No.	Substance.	Product.	M.P.	Yield.	Formuls.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	2,4-Dimethoxy-A	5-C	130°	71%	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl	57.5	57.9	5.5	5.7	15.8	16.5	..	..
2.	2,4-Dimethoxy-A	3,5-DC	110°	71	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ Cl ₂	52.0	52.0	5.3	5.5	25.8	25.6	..	..
3.	Methyl 2,4-dimethoxybenzoate	5-C	124°	89	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	54.0	54.0	5.2	5.3	14.3	14.5	..	..
4.	Methyl β-resorcylate	3,5-DC.	122°	41	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ Cl ₂	45.2	45.3	3.4	3.9	26.3	26.9	..	..
5.	2,4-Dimethoxy-Nb	5-C	116°	88	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₄ NCl	46.4	46.6	4.2	4.3	15.3	15.3	6.1	6.1
6.	2,6-Dihydroxy-Nb	3-C	120°	66	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄ NCl	41.4	41.3	2.5	2.9	17.7	17.4	6.6	6.9
7.	2,6-Dihydroxy-Nb	3,5-DC	144°	74	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₄ NCl ₂	38.2	38.1	2.9	2.8	28.0	28.2	5.6	5.8
8.	2,6-Dimethoxy-Nb	3-C	51°	86	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₄ NCl	46.8	46.6	4.1	4.3	15.2	15.3	6.4	6.1
9.	4,4'-Dihydroxy-Bp	3,3'-DC	178°	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₅ Cl ₂	59.2	59.4	4.5	4.3	25.4	25.1	..	..
10.	4,4'-Dimethoxy-Bp	3,3'-DC	145°	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ Cl ₂	61.7	61.7	5.3	5.1	22.7	22.8	..	..
11.	2,2'-Dimethoxy-Bp	5,4-DC	101°	66	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ Cl ₂	61.3	61.7	5.1	5.1	23.5	22.8	..	..

A=acetophenone; Nb=nitrobenzene, Bp=bi-phenyl; C=Chloromethyl; DC=dichloromethyl.

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones were prepared as usual and recrystallised from nitrobenzene.

TABLE II

Derivatives of the chloromethyl derivatives.

*S. No.	Substance.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	5-Acetoxyethyl	117°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃	62.3	62.0	6.5	6.4	..	..
2	3,5-Diacetoxyethyl	96°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₇	59.1	59.3	6.4	6.2	..	..
3	5-Acetoxyethyl	122°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃	58.7	58.2	6.1	5.9	..	..
5	5-Acetoxyethyl	113°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	51.5	51.8	5.1	5.1	5.4	5.5
	5-Methoxyethyl	112°	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	52.8	52.9	5.5	5.7	6.0	6.2
	5-Cyanomethyl	152°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂	53.8	54.1	4.3	4.5	12.5	12.6
7	3,5-Dicyanomethyl	182°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	51.7	51.5	3.0	3.0	18.3	18.0
10	3,3'-Diacetoxyethyl	154°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₆	66.7	67.0	6.1	6.1	..	..
	3,3'-Dimethoxyethyl	81°	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	71.1	71.5	7.3	7.3	..	..
11	5,5'-Diacetoxyethyl	70°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₆	67.4	67.0	6.3	6.1	..	..

* As recorded in Table I.

Oxidation of the Chloromethyl Derivatives.—The chloromethyl derivative was heated with an excess of KMnO₄ in presence of 10% NaOH solution over a steam bath for 8 hours. Sodium bisulphite was added to remove excess of permanganate. The mixture was filtered and acidified with HCl. The precipitated carboxy derivative was collected and recrystallised from either acetic acid or ethanol. In the case of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-dichloromethylbiphenyl, the oxidation was carried out in glacial acetic acid.

4,6-Dimethoxyisophthalic Acid.—A mixture of methyl 2,4-dimethoxy-5-acetylbenzoate² (1 g.), KMnO₄ (3 g.), and 10% NaOH solution (20 ml) was refluxed over a wire gauge for 4 hours. The acid obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 266°. (Found: C, 53.4; H, 4.7. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₀O₆: C, 53.1; H, 4.4%). Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained on oxidation of 2,4-dimethoxy-5-chloromethylacetophenone was not depressed. Eijkman *et al.*¹ who obtained the same acid by another method gave the same m.p.

Methyl 2,4-Dimethoxy-5-methylbenzoate.—Methyl 2,4-dimethoxy-5-chloromethylbenzoate (1g.) was taken in dioxan (20 ml) and zinc dust (3 g.) and HCl were added. When the reaction subsided, the solution was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water. The separated product was recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 151°. (Found: C, 62.8; H, 6.2. C₁₁H₁₄O₄ requires C, 62.9; H, 6.7%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-methylaniline.—2,4-Dimethoxy-5-chloromethylnitrobenzene was heated with tin and HCl on a steam bath for 2 hours. The resulting clear solution was made alkaline with NaOH and extracted with ether. The product obtained on removal of ether was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture, m.p. 91°. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 7.6; N, 8.3. C₉H₁₃O₂N requires C, 64.7; H, 7.8; N, 8.4%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-methylaniline was also obtained when the dimethyl ether of 4-methylresorcinol in glacial acetic acid was nitrated with HNO₃ (conc.) in the cold and the resulting nitro derivative was reduced with zinc and HCl. Mixed m.p. with the former was not depressed.

2,6-Dimethoxy-3-methylaniline.—2,6-Dimethoxy-3-chloromethylnitrobenzene was reduced with tin and HCl as above; m.p. 46°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 7.5; N, 8.4. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 64.7; H, 7.8; N, 8.4%.)

2,4-Dimethoxy-3-nitrobenzoic acid was prepared by oxidation of 2,6-dimethoxy-3-chloromethylnitrobenzene with alkaline $KMnO_4$; m.p. 215°. [Found: C, 47.7; H, 3.8; N, 6.4. Calc. for $C_9H_9O_6N$: C, 47.6; H, 3.9; N, 6.2%]

Dimethyl 2,2'-Dimethoxybiphenyl-5,5'-Dicarboxylate.—Methyl 3-iodo-4-methoxybenzoate (1 g.) was mixed with copper bronze (1g.) and heated at 180-200° in an oil bath for 1 hour. The mixture was extracted with hot benzene and the product obtained was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 170-72°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 5.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%.)

2,2'-Dimethoxybiphenyl-5,5'-dicarboxylic Acid.—The above ester (0.3 g.) was heated with ethanolic NaOH over a water bath for 1 hour and the clear solution obtained was acidified; the separated product (0.2 g.) was recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 335-40°. (Found after drying in vacuum at 120°: C, 63.4; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$: C, 63.6; H, 4.6%). Mixed m.p. with the product obtained on oxidation of 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-dichloromethylbiphenyl with alkaline $KMnO_4$ was not depressed. Gilman *et al.*³ who obtained it by another method recorded the same m.p.

4,4'-Dimethoxybiphenyl-3,3'-dicarboxylic Acid.—4,4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl was oxidised with alkaline $KMnO_4$ as usual and the product recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 236°. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 4.6. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 63.6; H, 4.6%). Mixed m.p. with the product obtained on oxidation of 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-dichloromethylbiphenyl with alkaline $KMnO_4$ was not depressed.

Acetoxymethyl Derivatives.—The chloromethyl derivative was mixed with glacial acetic acid and fused sodium acetate and heated over a water bath for 4 hours. The product separating on pouring into water was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture (Table II).

TABLE III

*Products of the Sommelet reaction on the chloromethyl derivatives.**

S.No.	Substance.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.			
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Formula.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
1	5-Formyl	167°	$C_{11}H_{12}O_4$	63.8	63.5	6.1	5.8	$C_{23}H_{20}O_{10}N_8$	275-77°	18.8	19.4
2	3,5-Diformyl	219°	$C_{12}H_{12}O_5$	61.2	61.0	5.1	5.1		> 300°	(c)	
3	5-Formyl	167°	$C_{11}H_{12}O_5$	59.4	59.9	5.4	5.4	$C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_4$	255-57°	13.7	13.9
5	5-Formyl	193°	$C_9H_9O_5N^a$	51.1	51.2	4.0	4.3	$C_{13}H_{13}O_8N_5$	> 300°	17.6	17.9
8	3-Formyl	102°	$C_9H_9O_5N^b$	51.2	51.2	4.7	4.3	$C_{13}H_{13}O_8N_5$	277-78°	17.9	17.9
10	3,3'-Diformyl	213°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	70.7	71.1	5.0	5.2	$C_{28}H_{24}O_{10}N_8$	> 300°	17.1	17.7
11	5,5'-Diformyl ^d	134°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	71.3	71.1	5.2	5.2	$C_{28}H_{24}O_{10}N_8$	> 300°	17.5	17.7

* As recorded in Table I.

a. Nitrogen found: 6.8; reqd. 6.6.

b. Nitrogen found: 6.1; reqd. 6.6.

c. Nitrogen found: 19.1. It analyses for di-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. $C_{24}H_{20}O_{11}N_8$ reqd. 18.8%.

d. Gattermann, *Annalen*, 1907, 357, 382. reports m.p. 130°.

Methoxymethyl Derivatives.—The chloromethyl derivative was heated with methanol and anhydrous potassium carbonate over a steam bath for 4 hours. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture (Table II).

Cyanomethyl Derivatives.—The chloromethyl derivative in acetone or methanol was heated over a water bath with potassium cyanide for 2 hours. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from benzene. In the case of 4,6-dihydroxy-3,5-dichloromethylnitrobenzene, the reaction mixture was acidified with HCl (Table II).

One of the authors (K. P. M.) thanks the Government of India for the award of a research training scholarship.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
M. S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODA.

Received January 7, 1963.